

Guidelines for the Documentation of Ethical, Legal and Social Issues (ELSI) in Cultural Data

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Table of Contents

Guidelines for the Documentation of Ethical, Legal and Social Issues (ELSI) in Cultural Data	1
Executive Summary.....	3
Introduction	3
Data Selection or Collection.....	6
Data Curation.....	10
Data Annotation	11
Information about Annotators.....	12
Data Documentation	14
Design of the Model.....	15
Model Creation	17
Application of the Model	19
Conclusion	20

Executive Summary

The machine learning models currently used under the heading ‘artificial intelligence’ (AI) have been trained almost exclusively on data from the 21st century. They are therefore highly unsuitable for use in historical contexts or contexts that differ culturally from the Western world. The provision of data from the cultural heritage sector does not simply provide a remedy here. Such datasets are usually of high quality and are characterised by their historical depth, cultural richness and diversity. However, they often contain problematic content that stems from the worldview of bygone times and therefore require comprehensive documentation in order to make machine learning models more precise, powerful and suitable for use in different cultural contexts, and to enable their use for the common good.

This guide focuses on ethical, social and legal aspects of documenting cultural heritage data used for training machine learning models. In particular, it focuses on how these models may perpetuate historical or statistical biases. The analysis moves along the different phases of the entire machine learning workflow and identifies a number of neuralgic points where biases can arise. In addition, the role of cultural heritage institutions is emphasised. These institutions have both extensive experience in establishing documentation procedures and valuable datasets. They are therefore particularly qualified to publish datasets accompanied by exemplary documentation. The provision of cultural heritage data, taking ethical considerations into account, can help to prepare critical content for society in a way that stimulates the development of AI applications and avoids socially detrimental effects. The guide concludes with a plea for an interdisciplinary approach to address the issues identified and emphasises the need for proactive measures by cultural heritage institutions to document existing stereotypes and biases in the data in order to make a positive contribution to AI ethics. In doing so, this guide not only opens up the possibility of contributing to the development of small-scale models that are highly suitable for specific tasks in the cultural heritage sector with a high cost-benefit ratio, but also of making the existing large-scale multipurpose models more robust, efficient, context-sensitive, accurate and sustainable. The publication of high-quality cultural heritage datasets, including documentation, sharpens the profile of the cultural heritage institution, makes it attractive as a partner for research and thus opens up the possibility of participating in the acquisition of research funding.

Introduction

Cultural heritage datasets come with their own history and provide set of challenges in terms of documenting ethical, legal and social issues. Generally speaking is the view of the world as manifested or presented in cultural heritage objects no longer congruent with today's perceptions. In addition, every cultural heritage collection represents a selection from the possible range of cultural objects to be preserved and may therefore be characterised by a less representative view. The authors of archival documents, e.g., were overwhelmingly men, as they were among those who were literate and socially privileged in history. Every employee of a cultural heritage institution and every historian is familiar with such a commonplace, but the members of the machine learning community are not, at least not as a matter of course. However, they are among the potential users of these datasets and are grateful to be informed about such statistical distortions in the data (also known as biases) through high-quality documentation. They are not only interested in questions of over-representation, but also those of under-representation, for example: Which social groups are systematically neglected in the datasets, which people are not addressed by name, which minorities are glossed over or only mentioned indirectly because they were not worth mentioning from the point of view of those in power at the time? Which groups of people could be harmed if a certain dataset – e.g. from colonial contexts – is used to train a machine learning model?

Ethical problems in the field of artificial intelligence (AI) are often addressed by a catalogue of abstract and prescriptive norms, which are addressed with terms such as statistical bias, transparency, explainability, privacy, data protection and copyright.¹ Accordingly, catalogues of principles and guidelines for research libraries focus on ‘accessibility, inclusion, neutrality, transparency, safety, humans in the loop and robustness’,² transparency and explainability,³ explainable artificial intelligence,⁴ the role of ethics in innovative processes,⁵ the role of research libraries in the formulation and implementation of institutional policy programmes,⁶ or in the regulation of AI in general.⁷ Elder codes of ethics, on the other hand, do not consider the peculiarities of digital objects, for example by focusing on physical property and conceptualising copies in terms of facsimiles.⁸ They often use normative language and prescriptive formulations of principles whose legitimacy derives from the recognition granted to international committees and associations.⁹

This guide aims to take a different approach by providing an overview of several phases in the creation of a machine learning model and using questions, explanations and examples at each individual step to show which ethical, legal or social aspects are relevant and need to be considered in each case. These steps are as follows: Data selection or collection, data curation, data annotation, information about annotators, data documentation, design of the model, model creation, application of the model.

The decisive motivation for going through individual phases relevant to modelling lies in the fact that each step involves people whose positionality can be determined; in this way, statements can be made about their influence. The concept of positionality was developed back in the 1980s by the science historian and feminist Donna Haraway. In her 1988 essay “Situated Knowledges”, she attempted to shed light on the tension between subjectivity and objectivity in the scientific community. She criticised the fact that science is nothing more than a rhetorical practice aimed at convincing others and gaining objective power. She describes the strategy of presenting knowledge as objective and impartial in order

¹ Kazim, E., & Koshiyama, A. S. (2021). A high-level overview of AI ethics. *Patterns*, 2(9), 100314. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2021.100314>.

² van Wessel, J. W. (2020). *AI in Libraries: Seven Principles*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.3865344>.

³ Ridley, M. (2022). Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI). *Information Technology and Libraries*, 41(2). <https://doi.org/10.6017/ital.v41i2.14683>.

⁴ Kennedy, M. L. (2019). What Do Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Ethics of AI Mean in the Context of Research Libraries? *Research Library Issues*, 299, 3–13. <https://doi.org/10.29242/rli.299.1>.

⁵ Johnson, S. A. (2019). Technology Innovation and AI Ethics. *Research Library Issues*, 299, 14–27. <https://doi.org/10.29242/rli.299.2>.

⁶ Henry, G. (2019). Research Librarians as Guides and Navigators for AI Policies at Universities. *Research Library Issues*, 299, 47–65. <https://doi.org/10.29242/rli.299.4>.

⁷ Bradley, F. (2022). Representation of Libraries in Artificial Intelligence Regulations and Implications for Ethics and Practice. *Journal of the Australian Library and Information Association*, 71(3), 189–200. <https://doi.org/10.1080/24750158.2022.2101911>.

⁸ ICOM (2017). *Code of Ethics*. <https://icom.museum/en/resources/standards-guidelines/code-of-ethics/>.

⁹ IFLA (2012). *IFLA Code of Ethics for Librarians and Other Information Workers (Long Version)*. <https://repository.ifla.org/handle/123456789/1850>.

to create the illusion of omniscience while concealing one's own position as "God's trick".¹⁰ She contrasts this rhetorical trick with seeing as a helpful metaphor for the production of knowledge. The "God's trick" disguises the act of seeing and thus the viewer himself by presenting a comprehensive knowledge or ethics imposed from above. By focussing on seeing as an active process in knowledge production, Haraway reveals that there is an observer, that this observer sees the world from a certain position and that her or his acquisition of this position is based on a history that determines how and what she or he sees. Situated knowledge is thus presented as the idea that subjects who recognise and reflect on their own presence in the process of knowledge and norm production can produce knowledge and values with greater objectivity than if they claim to be neutral. This is because we humans can only claim objective validity for our observations if we understand and account for the conditions under which we have made and understood our observations. Knowledge and values are valid under these situated conditions, they acknowledge their limited scope, and they invite the critical dialogue necessary to extend the validity of such knowledge beyond the boundaries of one's own community. A conscious and transparent positioning vis-à-vis the object of research improves the validity of scientific statements by recognising the social, cultural and political context of the knowledge produced. In the years following the publication of Haraway's essay, her critique was widely taken up and translated into self-reflexive methods.¹¹

The concept of positionality is ideally suited to scrutinise the various phases of creating a machine learning model. It is not uncommon for machine learning algorithms to be presented as neutral, mechanical, statistically based, authoritative entities without revealing the values that guide this scientific practice.¹² Furthermore, many machine learning studies suggest that there is an absolute truth value in relation to which the biases identifiable in the datasets are merely a deviation.¹³ The esoteric and exclusive language and the inaccessible technical vocabulary used by the machine learning community¹⁴ regrettably contribute to further asserting the claim to objectivity on a statistical basis and cementing its impartiality, safeguarding it against critical enquiry and making the general procedure and the individual work steps non-transparent. While biases are understood as statistical distortions in the field of statistics, there are other meanings of the term. For example, there are historical biases in datasets, i.e. the latter contain unfavourable representations of specific groups of people or reinforce historical stereotypes. In addition, machine learning models can be characterised by biases: Prediction biases can result from the annotations, aggregation biases can occur, or an algorithm can favour certain solutions and thus lead to an inductive bias of the model.

¹⁰ Haraway, D. (1988). Situated Knowledges: The Science Question in Feminism and the Privilege of Partial Perspective. *Feminist Studies*, 14(3), 575–599. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3178066>.

¹¹ Mey, G., & Mruck, K. (2011). *Grounded Theory Reader* (2., updated and enlarged ed.). VS Verlag für Sozialwissenschaften, pp. 427–448; Nelson, L. K. (2020). Computational Grounded Theory: A Methodological Framework. *Sociological Methods & Research*, 49(1), 3–42. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0049124117729703>.

¹² Birhane, A., Kalluri, P., Card, D., Agnew, W., Dotan, R., & Bao, M. (2022). The Values Encoded in Machine Learning Research. *2022 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*, 173–184. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3531146.3533083>.

¹³ Miceli, M., Posada, J., & Yang, T. (2022). Studying Up Machine Learning Data: Why Talk About Bias When We Mean Power? *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction*, 6(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3492853>.

¹⁴ Zuboff, S. (2019). *The Age of Surveillance Capitalism. The Fight for a Human Future at the New Frontier of Power* (First edition). Public Affairs, pp. 98–127.

A number of studies have shown that biases in data-driven systems can lead to discriminatory practices and exclusionary processes, i.e. that specific harm is caused to groups of people. This leads to a confusing situation: on the one hand, it is claimed that these biases can be combated and mitigated, the data cleansed and the systems debiased. On the other hand, it is obvious that biases are not just a technical phenomenon, but a social one, precisely because they can be found everywhere. However, if society as a whole is characterised by biases, then there will be no applications of artificial intelligence without bias.¹⁵ The only way to get to grips with this contradiction is to look at which biases are present where, what position people, datasets and models take in the respective phases of model creation and application and what effects this has.

Imagine that you are currently creating or have already compiled a dataset that you would now like to scrutinise in terms of ethical, legal and social aspects. The following questions and examples will help you to critically examine the dataset and consider ethical, legal and social aspects within the various phases of modelling.

Data Selection or Collection

How were the data selected? What systematics or classification systems are associated with this selection? What presuppositions or classificatory decisions does such a system imply?

As a human artefact, data are not simply 'given' (from Latin: datum), but result from an interest-driven world view or an interpretation of the world. This interpretation changes depending on the positionality of those who collect the data. Data are therefore not simply pre-existing and independent of humans, but a product of their engagement with the world around them, from which they extract the information relevant to them. As a result of human activity, data represent a decontextualised reduction of the world; as the cultural critic Johanna Drucker has put it, it can therefore also be described as 'taken' (from the Latin: capta),¹⁶ because it is actively shaped by people through selection, observation, interpretation and structuring. Although data are often described as neutral and objective and is surrounded by the aura of intersubjective transferability, generalisability and convertibility, its use depends heavily on the social context in which it is embedded. The philosopher of science Sabina Leonelli has therefore described data as a relational category that is applied to research results, serves as evidence for knowledge claims and is of interest to the researchers involved.¹⁷

On the one hand, structured data themselves represent classification systems; on the other hand, they are often linked to other classification systems that are added to the data records as metadata and therefore also have an impact on the training of machine learning models. The cataloguing of books in a library, for example, is a typical classification task in which the works are provided with labels or keywords; another example is the indexing of images with the classification concept ICONCLASS. Comprehensive classification systems such as keyword catalogues are integrated into information

¹⁵ Miceli et al., 2022, *ibid.*, p. 3.

¹⁶ Drucker, J. (2015). Graphical Approaches to the Digital Humanities. In S. Schreibman, R. Siemens, & J. Unsworth (eds.), *A New Companion to Digital Humanities* (pp. 238–250). John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781118680605.ch17>.

¹⁷ Leonelli, S. (2014). What difference does quantity make? On the epistemology of Big Data in biology. *Big Data & Society*, 1(1), 1–11, here p. 7. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2053951714534395>.

infrastructures and the work routines of librarians at national and international level, thus naturalising them and making them invisible.¹⁸ Classification systems are usually designed as ‘type cases’ whose boxes are formed by disjunctive classes or categories. Since the categories that make up the classification system are designed to be mutually exclusive and thus attempt to pigeonhole the entire world, neither the creators nor the users notice when real phenomena cannot be adequately captured. A good example of this is the International Classification of Diseases ICD, which is maintained by the WHO in Geneva; it represents the comprehensive Western view of the classification of diseases, forms the interface between therapists and insurance companies and is therefore extremely powerful; at the same time, however, it excludes the classification systems of other cultures, such as traditional Chinese medicine.¹⁹ Like all information systems, classification systems are imbued with ethical and political values. This becomes ethically questionable when, for example, the visibility of one group of people within the classification system is at the expense of another. For example, people who are not represented by the classification system are systematically disadvantaged, their allocation to a certain class is discriminatory or they are assigned to the residual category of the “other, further”, i.e. that which one does not know exactly how to categorise.²⁰

A famous example of distorted representations in a classification system is the Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH), which were criticised as early as 1971 by Sanford Berman. He pointed out that in the subject headings system, “tramps” and “unemployed” form a subcategory of “poor”, “Jewish criminals” and “Negro criminals” represent a separate category (whereas “Italian-American criminals” are missing), that “sexual perversion” is linked to “homosexuality” and “lesbianism” and that the term “gypsies” is cross-referenced with “rogues and vagabonds”.²¹ Overall, Berman criticised the racism, sexism, Christian-centred worldview and other biases in the LCSH. Since then, many of the keywords he criticised have been replaced. Similarly, other keyword systems used in libraries are also in a state of permanent change. Reflecting on the assumptions implicit in the classification systems therefore not only helps to reveal false or distorted representations, but also explains the way in which cultural heritage is interpreted and selected for digitisation. Furthermore, ethically problematic relationships arise when Western metadata schemes are used to describe and organise collections from colonial or indigenous contexts, or when digitised material that is sacred, secret or of particular importance to specific communities is created and made available online.²²

Which data subjects does this dataset include? Which perspectives are included in the dataset, and which are missing? Were these people involved in the design of the dataset and the data collection? Has the finalised dataset been validated by the data subjects?

The term ‘data subjects’ refers to the people contained in a dataset. These can be the authors of the articles, books or photos or the people depicted or described in the dataset. For the documentation, it is not only important that the explicitly named persons are described, but also the persons who are not

¹⁸ Bowker, G. C., & Star, S. L. (1999). *Sorting Things Out. Classification and its Consequences*. MIT Press, p. 47.

¹⁹ Bowker & Star, 1999, *ibid.*, p. 48/49.

²⁰ Bowker & Star, 1999, *ibid.*, p. 325.

²¹ Berman, S. (1971). *Prejudices and antipathies. A tract on the LC subject heads concerning people*. Scarecrow Press, pp. 183, 35/36, 182, 72.

²² Mindel, D. (2021). Ethics and digital collections: A selective overview of evolving complexities. *Journal of Documentation*, 78(3), 546–563, here p. 552. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JD-11-2020-0193>.

mentioned by name but are nevertheless included, because concealment or an indirect or collective address is part of the classic rhetoric of discrimination. This can also be seen, for example, in the fact that it is common practice in archives to create indexes with personal names as part of a collection description. These indices, like the collection descriptions, are a child of their time; what was considered important at the time of creation was indexed, while unimportant items were not – a typical example of positionality. As a result, finding aids for archival collections from colonial contexts sometimes list the names of the colonisers, but not those of the colonised, or only those of the male full citizens, but not those of the women and slaves.²³ It is precisely when a dataset reproduces stereotypes and reflects historical or contemporary discrimination against women and/or minorities that this is relevant for the users of this dataset. A representation of the world as it is or as it once was can therefore also be problematic from an ethical point of view. For example, a large dataset of digitised newspapers can also completely omit the history of a minority, as these people did not use the language of the newspaper; in this way, a ‘blind spot’ is created and prejudices against this group of people can be reinforced. This phenomenon is also known as historical bias.²⁴ It is not uncommon for datasets to contain sensitive information that can provide information about ethnic origin, sexual orientation, religious beliefs, political opinions or trade union membership. Image archives can, for example, contain photos of churches and funerals or documentation of protest demonstrations.²⁵ Even if such depictions are of a historical nature, it is advisable to report in the documentation that such sensitive information is contained in the dataset.

Cultural heritage institutions preserve material cultural assets so that contemporaries can learn about their origins and traditions. Cultural heritage is used to construct a range of identities and negotiate social and cultural values and meanings. The traditional collecting remit of cultural heritage institutions has historically led to the preservation of significant, influential and prestigious objects and artefacts that were seen as crucial to the shaping of modern nation states. It is therefore extremely informative for data consumers if such selection criteria are reflected. Furthermore, especially in the 19th and early 20th centuries, it was typical imperialist and colonialist behaviour to collect objects from other peoples from all over the world and bring them to the German Empire, an approach that has only recently been questioned. It is therefore now common practice for archives, manuscripts, cadastres or cult objects to be digitised in exchange with the indigenous groups whose tradition they belong to. Unlike a few decades ago, when cultural heritage institutions still decided authoritatively themselves what was to be collected, this process no longer takes place from above, but in an exchange on an equal footing. These groups of people are involved in the creation of the dataset and can help decide which objects are digitised and published, or whether a certain section of the dataset should not be published or only published with certain restrictions.²⁶

²³ Luthra, M., Todorov, K., Jeurgens, C., & Colavizza, G. (2024). Unsilencing Colonial Archives via Automated Entity Recognition. *Journal of Documentation*, 80(5), 1080–1105. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JD-02-2022-0038>.

²⁴ Suresh, H., & Guttag, J. (2021). A Framework for Understanding Sources of Harm throughout the Machine Learning Life Cycle. *Equity and Access in Algorithms, Mechanisms, and Optimization*, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3465416.3483305>.

²⁵ Wevers, M. (2022). *Fotopersbureau De Boer Training Set on Scene Detection* (Version 0.2) [Dataset]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7118409>.

²⁶ Guiliano, J., & Heitman, C. (2019). Difficult Heritage and the Complexities of Indigenous Data. *Journal of Cultural Analytics*. <https://doi.org/10.22148/16.044>.

In addition, documentation of the process of selecting objects for digitisation is of particular interest. Cultural heritage datasets are often the result of several staged selection processes. The various selection stages can be metaphorically described as a “ziggurat” structure, i.e. analogous to terraced buildings in ancient Mesopotamia.²⁷ The physical objects are selected from a basic population, from which in turn a number are selected for digitisation and so on. In most cases, however, nothing is known about the ‘totality’ of the historical records that once existed and from which the collection objects that are now stored in cultural heritage institutions were taken. Furthermore, what has been digitised represents in most cases only a fraction of a collection as a whole. This observation applies in particular to digitised archival materials. The motivations for digitisation differ a lot. As many digitisation projects are funded by the public sector, there are a whole range of different interests that guide the selection process. It is not uncommon for digitisation to be carried out as part of research projects, whereby the aim is not often to compile a representative selection based on specific research questions. Beyond research projects, a collection may be digitised for conservatory reasons or to preserve unique or rare objects.

Another specific feature of cultural heritage datasets is that many of them grow over time and can therefore be seen as dynamic, changing objects.²⁸ Digitised newspapers are a good example of this: Originally, conservation reasons prompted the digitisation of newspapers. In order to preserve decomposing material, such objects were among the first to be digitised in libraries; only later were these datasets systematically supplemented (or not). Collections of digitised newspapers are therefore a good example of how statistical skewness was introduced through the selection of material to be digitised.²⁹ Melody Beals and Emily Bell have documented a number of such biases using digitised newspapers. For example, newspapers were selected “that were of national influence”, “major national newspapers as well as influential and long-standing colonial, regional and local publications”, “a disproportionately large number of issues relating to the Second World War owing to targeted digitisation of this period through exceptional government funding” etc.³⁰

Generally speaking, the machine learning community has a strong interest in descriptive statistics of digital datasets, especially when derived from data science analyses, as well as information about how the content of such datasets has been affected by digitisation. Ideally, data documentation should therefore include a description of which part of a collection has been digitised and which has not, information about the main characteristics and further processing of the dataset (such as OCR), including state-of-the-art metrics.

Under which licence was the dataset published? Is the dataset or parts of it subject to copyright? What aspects of provenance influenced the data selection? How is legal access to the dataset organised? What are the terms

²⁷ Alkemade, H., Claeysens, S., Colavizza, G., Freire, N., Lehmann, J., Neudecker, C., Osti, G., & Van Strien, D. (2023). Datasheets for Digital Cultural Heritage Datasets. *Journal of Open Humanities Data*, 9, 17, S. 3/4. <https://doi.org/10.5334/johd.124>.

²⁸ Conway, P. (2015). Digital transformations and the archival nature of surrogates. *Archival Science*, 15(1), 51–69. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10502-014-9219-z>.

²⁹ Beelen, K., Lawrence, J., Wilson, D. C. S., & Beavan, D. (2023). Bias and representativeness in digitized newspaper collections: Introducing the environmental scan. *Digital Scholarship in the Humanities*, 38(1), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1093/lhc/fqac037>.

³⁰ Beals, M. H. & Bell, E. (2020). *The Atlas of Digitised Newspapers and Metadata: Reports from Oceanic Exchanges*. Loughborough: 2020. <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.11560059>.

of use of the dataset? Have the data subjects given their consent to inclusion in the dataset? Was informed consent given, was consent voluntary and revocable? How is the anonymity of the data subjects protected? Is some of the data only intended for restricted use by certain communities?

Data consumers are very interested in the answers to these questions in order to be able to assess whether the dataset is suitable for the intended purposes. Even anonymised datasets do not necessarily guarantee complete data protection; combined with other datasets, they can enable the re-identification of data subjects. Data consumers may also be interested in the ethical handling of datasets. They will therefore want to know how the terms of use or code of conduct of the organisation providing the data are structured so that they can behave in accordance with them – in word and in spirit.

Data Curation

Who compiled this dataset? Who or which institution financed it? What were the motivations or objectives? Was the positionality of the data curators or other employees recorded in the documentation?

The work of data curators and researchers in cultural heritage institutions can be understood in a similar way to the process of data construction and collection undertaken by researchers: They select objects to be digitised or process existing data based on certain criteria, norms and practices; a whole range of social, cultural, organisational and technological processes have an impact on the dataset and thus inscribe the positionality of the actors and the cultural heritage institutions into the dataset. The curation of datasets inevitably involves decisions that affect the design of the dataset as a whole, such as how the dataset is structured, which language(s) are used, which perspectives are considered and who will annotate.³¹ These conscious decisions made during curation are responsible for why datasets and machine learning models work better for certain populations than others. The variability of the selection decisions shows that, despite predetermined criteria, working on and with data must be understood as a dynamic process. Because datasets can be easily modified (updating metadata or importing improved OCR results, deleting and replacing distorted digitised material, converting to other data formats, etc.), they are not simply the equivalent of physical collections in cultural heritage institutions, but should be understood as dynamic, changeable objects.³² Against this background, it becomes clear that a generous documentation of cultural heritage data should also provide information about the interests, motivations and goals of the curators, the people involved in the data selection and the institution or organisation providing the data, especially regarding the choices made with respect to the population groups represented in the dataset. Complete documentation specifies the respective function or role of the persons involved and thus reveals the positionality of the data curators and their colleagues. This can vary greatly in detail, depending on who was involved in selecting the material to be digitised (or born-digital), whether this was done as part of a research project or was aimed more at preserving material at risk of destruction, or to document the various stages of selection processes that a collection often goes through before it is available as a dataset. One example of this is the datasheet for the dataset

³¹ Santy, S., Liang, J., Le Bras, R., Reinecke, K., & Sap, M. (2023). NLPositionality: Characterizing Design Biases of Datasets and Models. *Proceedings of the 61st Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 1: Long Papers)*, 9080–9102. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2023.acl-long.505>.

³² Conway, P. (2015). Digital transformations and the archival nature of surrogates. *Archival Science*, 15(1), 51–69. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10502-014-9219-z>.

“Unsilencing Colonial Archives via Automated Entity Recognition”, which contains information on the publishing institution, the funding and the various tasks and roles of the data curators involved.³³

Data Annotation

How were the data annotated? What values do the annotations represent? Have the annotations been aggregated? Are the annotation guidelines available? What are the limitations of the annotation method?

Datasets specially prepared for machine learning contain annotations, i.e. qualifications of individual elements (‘instances’) of the dataset. These can be classifying labels for images (“this is a dog”, “this is a cat”, “this is a headline” or similar), but they can also be ratings by the annotators (e.g. “good”, “bad”, “okay”, “toxic” or numerical values on a Likert scale). These annotations are usually not only expensive (as they are made by humans), but also crucial for training a model. Therefore, the machine learning community is very interested in information about the origin and process followed to create the annotations. Typically, annotators are provided with instructions on how to perform the annotations; it is helpful to at least link to or explain these guidelines. The fact that the devil is in the detail when it comes to classifications should have been made clear in the section above under “Data selection or collection” – missing classes, a lack of differentiation options and collection categories for elements that are difficult to categorise are typical limitations here. If an assessment is made by the annotation, then this is usually dependent on the cultural background or socio-demographic characteristics of the annotators. The assumption that there are universal, i.e. valid for all of humanity and therefore objective classifications or evaluations is extremely questionable. It may be possible to distinguish between cats and dogs, but it is not so easy to distinguish between men and women. The simple question of whether it is good to eat with your hands is certainly answered differently by Central Europeans than by Indians or Ethiopians, and therefore depends heavily on the cultural context, table manners and ideas of hygiene.

Such value judgements are not simply subjective, but are similar for groups of people, as they depend on socialisation and cultural conditioning and therefore form stable structures and patterns. Major differences are particularly evident in the evaluation of natural language: for example, there may be little agreement as to whether a statement is perceived as problematic by an annotator or not. A complex sentence such as “Iran's Supreme Court claims gender equality is ‘Zionist plot’ aiming to corrupt role of women in society. I fucking second that!” is unanimously regarded as hateful speech by annotators of the Jewish faith, but not by Muslims, while annotators of the Christian faith tend to disagree on how they should evaluate the sentence.³⁴ Also, utterances that are presented in a certain sociolect (e.g. “Berliner Schnauze”) or that can be assigned to a clear political direction can lead to very different evaluations. It is therefore important that those drafting the annotation guidelines consider the possibility that people with different social and cultural backgrounds will come to different judgements.³⁵ Cultural heritage in particular shows that values change over time: different times, different customs. The annotation of digitised cultural heritage will therefore always generate differences that result firstly from the temporal

³³ Luthra, M., Todorov, K., Wissen, L. van, Jeurgens, C., & Colavizza, G. (2022). *Unsilencing Colonial Archives via Automated Entity Recognition* [Dataset]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7129316>.

³⁴ Santy et al., 2023, *ibid.*, p. 9085.

³⁵ Díaz, M., Kivlichan, I., Rosen, R., Baker, D., Amironesei, R., Prabhakaran, V., & Denton, E. (2022). CrowdWorkSheets: Accounting for Individual and Collective Identities Underlying Crowdsourced Dataset Annotation. *2022 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*, 2342–2351. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3531146.3534647>.

difference between the cultural heritage object and the annotator, and secondly from the different levels of knowledge of the annotators depending on their social, cultural, etc. background. background of the annotators. A good example of this is the evaluation of ethically problematic language from the 19th or early 20th century by contemporary annotators.³⁶ The contemporary view of historical material expressed in an annotation therefore illustrates the idea of positionality, as it represents an external perspective to which an interpretation is inscribed.

In machine learning, it is currently common practice to ‘aggregate’ divergent annotations, i.e. to merge them into a single value. This can be done by using the label that is present in the absolute or relative majority of the datasets, or by adding a weight to the label, or by making the model use only one class. From a machine learning perspective, dealing with “statistical noise” in this way can make sense, but from an ethical perspective, the “tyranny of the mean” is problematic when it comes to value judgements.³⁷ It can therefore make sense to publish datasets with non-aggregated annotations or to publish all annotations separately, as these support the diversity of perspectives and the disclosure of the positionality contained in the annotations. It is then up to the developers to decide how to deal with disaggregated annotations and which modelling technique to use to deal with the inherent differences and distributions.

Information about Annotators

What socio-demographic information is available about the annotators? Can the annotators be assigned to a specific population group? Are the socio-demographic data on the annotators available to the users of the dataset?

In 2010, the evolutionary psychologist Joseph Henrich and two colleagues published a fundamental critique of the methodology of psychological studies by taking a systematic look at who actually makes up the population analysed in these studies.³⁸ In psychology, these are for the most part the students of this degree programme. Henrich's essay is entitled “The weirdest people in the world?” This play on words can be resolved insofar as WEIRD stands for “white, educated, industrialised, rich, democratic”. Henrich thus criticises the fact that the entire discipline of psychology, as well as cognitive science, economics and the behavioural sciences as a whole, is based on the study of a small section of the population of the Western world – a clear case of bias. In the study, WEIRD people are contrasted with small-scale societies (such as tribes), non-Western industrialised societies, non-American Western societies and non-studied US-Americans. The assumption that the small population group of WEIRD people is representative because there is little variation among human populations is systematically refuted, as is the possibility of deriving any generalisations from the studies conducted. Instead, WEIRD people are described as statistical outliers compared to other populations; this is the reason why Henrich

³⁶ Brate, R., Nesterov, A., Vogelmann, V., van Ossenbruggen, J., Hollink, L., & van Erp, M. (2021). Capturing Contentiousness: Constructing the Contentious Terms in Context Corpus. *Proceedings of the 11th on Knowledge Capture Conference*, 17–24. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3460210.3493553>.

³⁷ Talat, Z., Blix, H., Valvoda, J., Ganesh, M. I., Cotterell, R., & Williams, A. (2022). On the Machine Learning of Ethical Judgments from Natural Language. *Proceedings of the 2022 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies*, 769–779. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2022.naacl-main.56>.

³⁸ Henrich, J., Heine, S. J., & Norenzayan, A. (2010). The weirdest people in the world? *Behavioral and Brain Sciences*, 33(2–3), 61–83. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0140525X0999152X>.

describes them as ‘strange’ and as the “worst population on which to base our understanding of *Homo sapiens*”.³⁹

As a rule, machine learning datasets are either processed by annotators who correspond to the WEIRD people⁴⁰ – this is particularly true in the field of natural language, especially English –, or the annotators are recruited via crowdsourcing platforms such as Amazon's Mechanical Turk; they then come from non-WEIRD populations from the USA and India, especially when it comes to language-related tasks such as “analysis and interpretation”,⁴¹ or from Latin American contexts.⁴² There is no doubt that such different groups of annotators bring a very different positionality to the datasets, and it represents a clear added value if the documentation accompanying the dataset provides information about the anonymised socio-demographic data of the annotators. This also makes it possible to quantify the positionality: The annotations can be grouped according to certain demographic characteristics and the correlation between the two variables can be calculated. The ranking of the correlations can be used to show which demographic subgroup of annotators best corresponds to the positionality of the dataset (and consequently later also of the model). The disagreement among the annotators with regard to the assignment of labels can also be calculated by determining the mean value and the variance of the annotations for a specific annotator group for each label assigned.⁴³ If there is no information about the annotators for an annotated dataset, the positionality of this dataset can still be determined ex post by re-annotating the data a second time by annotators with known socio-demographic information and comparing their annotations with the previously assigned annotations so that the positionality of the unknown annotators can be inferred.

Economic considerations often take centre stage when selecting annotators. If it is not the researchers themselves and their students – and thus WEIRD people – then crowd workers are often used on the basis of their previous performance values to enable the most cost-effective creation of annotations. Factors such as special knowledge or experience with complex material, on the other hand, are often neglected.⁴⁴ This is rarely unproblematic; with regard to industrial machine learning datasets, it makes sense to anticipate the possible social application contexts of these datasets and the models trained on them, as well as the marginalised communities they encompass, and to select annotators with comparable socio-demographic characteristics. With regard to datasets from the cultural heritage sector, on the other hand, the expertise that enables the annotators to adequately situate and assess content from historical contexts will be decisive. In any case, rigorous documentation and publication of the decisions and results associated with the annotation of datasets is recommended.

³⁹ Henrich et al., 2010, *ibid.*, p. 82.

⁴⁰ Santy et al., 2023, *ibid.*, p. 9082.

⁴¹ Hube, C., Fetahu, B., & Gadiraju, U. (2019). Understanding and Mitigating Worker Biases in the Crowdsourced Collection of Subjective Judgments. *Proceedings of the 2019 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 1–12, here p. 2. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3290605.3300637>; Santy et al., 2023, *ibid.*, p. 9083.

⁴² Miceli et al., *ibid.*, 2022, p. 6ff.

⁴³ Santy et al., 2023, *ibid.*, p. 9085.

⁴⁴ Díaz et al., 2022, *ibid.*, pp. 2/3.

Data Documentation

What does the documentation that accompanies the publication of a dataset or a trained model look like? According to which standards or formats was this documentation created?

Especially in archives – but also in libraries – there is a long tradition of documentation in the form of collection descriptions. In these institutions, the technical language and procedures have therefore already been developed to compile collections according to aspects such as power, inclusivity or data protection, and documentation practices and quality criteria for the description of such collections have also been developed. The realisation that this practice is also exemplary for the field of machine learning and in particular with regard to the compilation of datasets was only made public in the relevant community a few years ago by two researchers.⁴⁵ Both authors criticise the lack of an industry-wide standard for fair data collection and highlight the accuracy and rigour with which archivists and librarians approach the creation of collections and the accompanying documentation as exemplary for the machine learning community. They also praise the fact that archives generally have a dedicated mission statement that sets out principles or concepts of collection principles, that curators are employed full-time to weigh up the benefits and risks of compiling different data or to discuss which set of rules to apply, and that such institutions have codes of ethics and/or codes of conduct and procedures in place in the event that these are breached, and that standardised forms of documentation are available. From the perspective of a cultural heritage institution, it may come as something of a surprise that until a few years ago, there was no requirement to publish comprehensive accompanying documentation in the field of machine learning. However, it is only in recent years that numerous examples have become known in which groups of people have suffered systematic disadvantages from the application of machine learning models. Previously, this was more an area of research; concrete applications in the financial sector, healthcare, legal cases or the selection of job applicants, for example, remained the exception rather than the rule. In a rapidly developing field in which the frequency of publication of datasets and models is constantly increasing, it is therefore not surprising that standards, formats and good practice examples first need to be developed.

However, it is also important to recognise some fundamental differences that exist between datasets created by cultural heritage institutions and those that come from the machine learning field. The values that guide the field of machine learning, such as performance, generalisation, efficiency, building on past work and novelty (of the approach),⁴⁶ have little to do with the values that are implicitly or explicitly contained in the mission statements of cultural heritage institutions. Critics therefore criticise, for example, that in the machine learning field, efficiency comes at the expense of accuracy, universal applicability at the expense of context, alleged objectivity at the expense of positionality and work on the models at the expense of engagement with the datasets.⁴⁷ The premise for the creation of datasets in the field of machine learning is often the size of the dataset (‘the bigger the better’), whereas it is precisely the task of cultural heritage institutions to select what is important, valuable and worth

⁴⁵ Jo, E. S., & Gebru, T. (2020). Lessons from archives: Strategies for collecting sociocultural data in machine learning. *Proceedings of the 2020 Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*, 306–316. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3351095.3372829>.

⁴⁶ Birhane et al., 2022, *ibid.*, p. 174.

⁴⁷ Scheuerman, M. K., Hanna, A., & Denton, E. (2021). Do Datasets Have Politics? Disciplinary Values in Computer Vision Dataset Development. *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction*, 5(CSCW2), 1–37. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3476058>.

preserving from the mass of available material, i.e. to reduce it. Furthermore, the fields have different tasks and objectives. While the machine learning field focuses on the development of practical applications or the achievement of certain accuracy values, the cultural heritage field serves the purpose of remembering and preserving, is orientated towards the current legal framework and data protection regulations and places great value on the accessibility and indexability of collections.

Standardised forms of documentation have in fact only been proposed in the field of machine learning in recent years, both with regard to datasets⁴⁸ and for the models themselves,⁴⁹ especially with regard to making the biases that inevitably exist in datasets transparent and averting potential harm to those population groups affected by the application of machine learning models. These templates for the documentation of datasets and models usually contain catalogues of questions and are structured along areas such as data collection, annotation, contextualisation and areas of application.⁵⁰ Specific templates have also been developed for the cultural heritage sector.⁵¹ These examples aim to raise awareness for better documentation, to create transparency, especially with regard to the provenance of the data, the context of their origin, their possible use (and possibly harmful use, if assessable) and the biases.

Design of the Model

What decisions were made by the researchers, developers or data scientists during the design? Which of these are documented? Which biases can result from this?

In order to create a machine learning model, researchers, developers and data scientists make a whole series of decisions that are within their scope of judgement and that are made along the entire machine learning workflow. Through these decisions, the developers' positionality is inscribed in the modelling process. If there is not an already annotated dataset, these decisions can start with the creation and curation of the datasets, i.e. selecting the sources, deciding which language(s) to use, which population groups the dataset will and will not include, and how the annotations will be made.⁵² The researchers

⁴⁸ Gebru, T., Morgenstern, J., Vecchione, B., Vaughan, J. W., Wallach, H., Daumé III, H., & Crawford, K. (2021). Datasheets for Datasets. *Communications of the ACM*, 64(12), 86–92. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3458723>.

⁴⁹ Mitchell, M., Wu, S., Zaldivar, A., Barnes, P., Vasserman, L., Hutchinson, B., Spitzer, E., Raji, I. D., & Gebru, T. (2019). Model Cards for Model Reporting. *Proceedings of the Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*, 220–229. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3287560.3287596>.

⁵⁰ Comp. here besides Gebru et al., 2021, *ibid.* and Mitchell et al., 2019, *ibid.* also Pushkarna, M., Zaldivar, A., & Kjartansson, O. (2022). Data Cards: Purposeful and Transparent Dataset Documentation for Responsible AI. *2022 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*, 1776–1826. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3531146.3533231>; Richards, J. T., Piorkowski, D., Hind, M., Houde, S., Mojsilovic, A., & Varshney, K. R. (2021). A Human-Centered Methodology for Creating AI FactSheets. *IEEE Data Eng. Bull.*, 44(4), 47–58. <http://sites.computer.org/debull/A21dec/p47.pdf>.

⁵¹ Alkemade, H., Claeysens, S., Colavizza, G., Freire, N., Lehmann, J., Neudecker, C., Osti, G., & Van Strien, D. (2023). Datasheets for Digital Cultural Heritage Datasets. *Journal of Open Humanities Data*, 9, 17. <https://doi.org/10.5334/johd.124>; Eskevich, M., & Luthra, M. (2024). Data-Envelopes for Cultural Heritage: Going beyond Datasheets. In I. Siegert & K. Choukri (eds.), *Proceedings of the Workshop on Legal and Ethical Issues in Human Language Technologies @ LREC-COLING 2024* (pp. 52–65). ELRA and ICCL. <https://aclanthology.org/2024.legal-1.9>; Lee, B. C. G. (2023). The „Collections as ML Data“ Checklist for Machine Learning & Cultural Heritage. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1002/asi.24765>.

⁵² Santy et al., 2023, *ibid.*, p. 9083.

usually design the annotation task with regard to the prediction task that the model has to fulfil. The annotation guidelines are formulated accordingly. The annotators are then selected, i.e. the decision is often made between a group of experts (the researchers themselves, students, WEIRD people) and a provider of a crowdsourcing platform. In the latter case, the task is distributed across a network and the crowd workers create the labels of the training dataset on which the model is trained. As described above, the personal attitude of the annotators can be expressed in the assigned labels.

In the next phase, the selection made by the researchers from various options plays an even more decisive role. Firstly, the annotated dataset is pre-processed. Typically, the labels assigned by the annotators are validated by calculating the inter-rater reliability or inter-annotator agreement, for example Krippendorff's alpha or Cohen's kappa. There is no measure that is generally and consistently applied in the field of machine learning, and there is no consensus among experts on a threshold value above which the annotations are discarded.⁵³ Rather, the choice of the measure of judgement agreement or threshold is at the discretion of the researchers. The labels are then usually aggregated to create a single perspective from which the machine learning algorithm derives the target and creates the model. As explained above, the label that was used in the absolute or relative majority is often used in the aggregation. The term 'ground truth' must therefore be understood in context and as relative; there is no absolute truth in this approach.

In the next step, the researchers deal with the selection of suitable ML architectures, frameworks and algorithms and test various parameter settings that should influence the learning behaviour. The aim is to learn a function (a model) that describes the training data, including defined labels, as accurately as possible and at the same time can also generate good results on new, as yet unseen data. Loss functions and evaluation metrics can be used for orientation. In this phase, the data scientists deal with the assumptions they have made about the scope of the model. These assumptions strongly influence the exploratory data analyses and the selection of models and are therefore fundamental to the decisions made. In addition, it is possible to test a whole range of models and evaluate the results comparatively. The idea behind this is to take a decision in favour of one of the models based on the comparison and to determine how each of them has come about using different algorithmic and statistical methods, which errors occur in each case or which of the models shows the best performance on the test set.⁵⁴ In the best case, the assumptions about the scope are reflected in the documentation accompanying the dataset or model, thus revealing the basis on which the researchers arrived at the judgements they made.

The process just described illustrates the many options from which data scientists must choose and in which their positionality becomes clear. Nevertheless, this process can be regarded as ideal-typical for the field of research and thus corresponds roughly to the procedure applied in the case of the utilisation of cultural heritage data. In the private sector, on the other hand, this process can be much more complicated, as there are a number of other interests and stakeholders involved, so that the entire process of modelling design must be understood as a complex negotiation process. This can already affect the phase of formulating the task, but also the choice of methods, instruments and data. Economic

⁵³ Cambo, S. A., & Gergle, D. (2022). Model Positionality and Computational Reflexivity: Promoting Reflexivity in Data Science. *CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 1–19, here p. 15. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3491102.3501998>.

⁵⁴ Cambo & Gergle, 2022, *ibid.*, p. 3.

considerations with regard to competing products, the usually expensive manual data annotation, the practical implementation of the machine learning workflow or the company goals to be achieved all play a role here.⁵⁵

Biases can occur or influence the model during the model design phase. A typical example here is the choice of language. Data scientists may favour a particular language because they are familiar with it and are therefore better able to judge the labels assigned by the annotators. Or they may choose English, for example, because it has the most data available. Another typical bias arises when a created model performs differently for different populations. For example, if it has been trained to recognise certain features of a natural language for a particular population group in a particular country, it may perform well in a similar application context, but in a different population group and a culturally and geographically different context in which the same language is spoken, this may not be the case and performance may drop sharply. Another example is the prediction of social acceptance, which is highly dependent on socio-demographic variables, contextual factors and the changing norms and values of a society over time.⁵⁶ Employees in cultural heritage institutions are very aware of such peculiarities in the data, whereas this cannot be taken for granted with data scientists. There is therefore much to be said in favour of interdisciplinary and intersectoral cooperation in the model design phase, because the quality of a model depends heavily on the task for which it was trained and thus on the assumptions about the model's area of application. This also illustrates why it is not simply possible and can lead to problems if a machine learning model has been trained on cultural heritage data and is then used in a completely different context.

Model Creation

Whose positionality and viewpoint does the model rely on for its prediction? Which positionalities and perspectives are projected by the model into unseen data? What biases characterise the model?

The discussion about biases in machine learning centres almost exclusively on statistical distortions in the datasets. In contrast, comparatively little attention is paid to the fact that biases can also arise during the modelling process. Obviously, the myth that models, once created, are objective, unbiased and impartial is part of the well-cultivated 'aura of objectivity' that the positionality or situated knowledge approach questions. The creation of "Model Cards for Model Reporting" was initiated not least in order to counter this myth and to document the biases that characterise a model.⁵⁷

The fact that models also have their own positionality becomes clear when they are localised in the larger context of a socio-technical system. In a broader sense, this includes the social, cultural and political context, and in a narrower sense, the economic and organisational context in which the machine learning workflow is embedded. Of particular relevance here is the origin of a model from the data on which it was trained, but also the application of the model on data for which it provides predictions. In order to grasp the positionality of a model, however, it is not enough to understand it as a productive element in a long chain of individual steps. Rather, it is helpful to bear in mind that the behaviour of a trained machine learning model can be characterised by comparing it with the behaviour of people who

⁵⁵ Passi, S., & Sengers, P. (2020). Making data science systems work. *Big Data & Society*, 7(2), 1–13.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/2053951720939605>.

⁵⁶ Santy et al., 2023, *ibid.*, p. 9085ff.

⁵⁷ Mitchell et al., 2019, *ibid.*

perform the same or a comparable task as the model. By comparing this with human behaviour (e.g. when assessing toxic comments or social acceptance), it then becomes clear which perspectives the model reproduces and automates in a privileged way, which perspectives it tends to neglect and which ones it does not consider, and which perspectives it does not agree with at all. Models often automate a single perspective on the target object, even if the labels of the training dataset contain a variety of different perspectives. The juxtaposition with human behaviour makes it possible to outline and determine the position from which the model ‘sees’ the world.⁵⁸ This makes it very clear that a model by no means represents omniscient and comprehensive objectivity and thus imitates the “God’s trick”, but that the positionality of a model only represents a partial view of the world.

Determining the positionality of a model first becomes clear when one considers the annotations that have been added to the dataset by human annotators and that result from the annotation guidelines created by the researchers or data scientists. Statistical techniques such as unsupervised clustering can be used to match the model positionality with the existing annotations and determine the divergences; this can identify groups of annotators who add similar annotations to similar objects in a dataset, and their position can be contrasted with that of the model. This technique is called “position mining”.⁵⁹ It is undoubtedly very time-consuming to use such an analysis technique to better understand model positionality, but it is a good example of what this means. However, this example falls back on the datasets on which the model is based and the biases contained therein.

On the other hand, it must be emphasised that the behaviour of a model and the prediction biases that characterise it do not only result from the training data. As a consequence, demographically poorly balanced datasets would then lead to poorly balanced model predictions, and demographically well balanced datasets would lead to balanced models; then only the underlying data would have to be changed in order to contain the bias of a model. In contrast, however, there is also an inductive bias in learning algorithms, which can lead to one group of annotators or their annotations being favoured over others, regardless of how these groups are represented in the dataset. More generally, the favouring of solutions by a machine learning algorithm before it sees new data is described as inductive bias, with each of these algorithms showing different inductive biases depending on the assumptions about how the data relates to the real world. This bias can also be identified and described by position mining, thus determining the positionality of the model.⁶⁰ In this way, it is possible to better understand who benefits from the behaviour of the model and who is disadvantaged by it; preventing possible damage is then, again, the task of the model design.

The insight that a model also has its own positionality and is characterised not only by the underlying training data, but also by an inductive bias, once again underlines the possibility that the predictions of a model can also lead to serious disadvantages for individual groups of people, whether due to the fact that the predictions made by the model can be discriminatory towards certain groups and be described as toxic, or because certain groups of people are systematically disadvantaged in the granting of credit. In any case, such ethically questionable results speak for a reflection on the positionality of a model, especially through an interdisciplinary dialogue between social and information scientists, and for a documentation of the positionality and the model-inherent biases in the corresponding model card.

⁵⁸ Cambo & Gergle, 2022, *ibid.*, p. 4.

⁵⁹ Cambo & Gergle, 2022, *ibid.*, p. 7f.

⁶⁰ Cambo & Gergle, 2022, *ibid.*, p. 8.

Application of the Model

To what extent can people be harmed by the application of a model? What different types of harm are conceivable through the application of a model? Who determines what is considered a harmful bias?

Statistically skewed datasets do not cause harm per se. It is only the application of trained models that can lead to undesirable and ethically questionable social effects, partly because they reinforce the biases of the underlying datasets. Roughly speaking, the possible harms that occur when using a model can be divided into two groups: allocative and representative harms. So-called allocative harms occur when an automated system unfairly distributes resources (e.g. loans) or future opportunities (e.g. jobs) to different population groups. Representation harms occur when an automated system presents a population group in a disadvantageous, stereotypical, discriminatory or degrading way or causes it to disappear.⁶¹

Obviously, societal harms arise particularly easily when a model is used for a purpose for which it was not conceived. For example, a model is trained on a dataset that represents a particular population group, but is applied to a dataset that represents a different population group. In terms of cultural heritage datasets, this is easy to understand: If a particular population group is portrayed in an unfavourable way in a dataset created on the basis of historical material, this bias will still have an effect on contemporary data material even if social conditions have fundamentally changed. Historical stereotypes can thus be extended into the present or even reinforced.

In addition, the models can be adapted to existing data in order to achieve better results or to better fulfil the requirement for explainability. These adaptation processes can again generate biases in the model. In learning algorithms, aggregation biases can occur when a universal model is used for data that are based on groups or example types that should be considered different. This bias is based on the assumption that the assignment between labels and the individual instances is consistent across the entire dataset. However, this is often not the case. When people of different cultures, regional origins and values are brought together in a comprehensive dataset, one and the same variable associated with each of these groups can mean different things. As a result, the aggregation bias means that the model does not work optimally for any of these groups, or it only fits well for the largest group.⁶²

A model is usually optimised on the basis of its training data; however, the quality of a model is often evaluated with benchmark datasets and different models can thus be compared with each other. An evaluation bias can occur here if these benchmark data do not represent the population to which the model is applied. This encourages the use of models that only work well on the subset of data represented by the benchmark data.

Knowledge of the context and purpose of a model is therefore crucial. However, contextual knowledge in particular cannot be taken for granted in the machine learning community. Understanding bias in historical material, for example, requires knowledge of how structural oppression and discrimination were practised in the past, how linguistic representation and social stratification are related, and how

⁶¹ Blodgett, S. L., Barocas, S., Daumé III, H., & Wallach, H. (2020). Language (Technology) is Power: A Critical Survey of “Bias” in NLP. *Proceedings of the 58th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, 5454–5476, here p. 5455. <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2020.acl-main.485>.

⁶² Suresh & Guttag, 2021, *ibid.*, p. 5.

this has changed over time. Cultural heritage records require a deep understanding of a gradual change in norms and positionality. The fact that on the one hand it seems easy to identify ethical deficits in societies one or more centuries removed does not mean that it is equally easy to determine exactly how a complex socio-technological system affects specific populations. In other words, it is a challenge to assess whether a bias inherent in the system has a harmful effect on a population group, to what extent this happens and who exactly is affected. Mastering this challenge also means reflecting on the asymmetrical power relations between those who are within the socio-technological system and those who are affected by its impact.

Conclusion

In recent decades, significant investments have been made across Europe in the digitisation of cultural heritage. Most of this expenditure has been financed by public funding, so the datasets created are intended both for private use and for innovation and research. Datasets from cultural heritage institutions are of great interest for research and development because – unlike data collected on the internet – they are of a particularly high quality: They have often gone through several selection stages and the curation as well as the creation of metadata in catalogues and indices has been carried out by well-trained specialists. Bibliographic references from libraries are just as attractive as high-quality text data resulting from the digitisation of library holdings. Unlike the content of many websites, these collections are of high linguistic and orthographic quality, as they were first selected by editors in the publishing houses and then linguistically checked. According to a study, high-quality English-language text data will be exhausted before 2026;⁶³ against this background, further digitisation efforts are welcome. In addition to mass digitisation projects of books, cultural heritage institutions are already providing high-quality digitisation of three-dimensional objects, for example, and will do so even more in the future, and the use of state-of-the-art techniques such as motion capture, photogrammetry, linear and laser scanning, panoramic videos or stereographic panoramas will increase. In the field of document analysis, the focus of research will shift from layout analysis and text recognition to information extraction, which will result in even more high quality and cross-linked data.

Not only the provision of the data themselves, but also the provision of well-founded accompanying documentation represents a gain for research and development. Cultural heritage institutions can build on long-established and practised documentation practices. The reflexivity and localisation of one's own positionality, which this guide explains, serves not only to document content that is problematic from an ethical, legal or social perspective, but also to strengthen the active role of cultural heritage practitioners in the process of making digital content available and circulating it.

By publishing high-quality cultural heritage datasets together with accompanying documentation, cultural heritage institutions not only demonstrate that they are able to provide content that can be utilised in a computational manner; they also raise the profile of the institution, become attractive partners for research and can thus participate in the acquisition of research funding. Finally, as institutions with a wealth of experience in the description of collections, they are ideally suited to develop and document best practices and knowledge acquired through experience as well as standards in a highly dynamic field.

⁶³ Villalobos, P., Ho, A., Sevilla, J., Besiroglu, T., Heim, L., & Hobbhahn, M. (2024). Position: Will we run out of data? Limits of LLM scaling based on human-generated data. *Proceedings of the 41st International Conference on Machine Learning*, 49523–49544. <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.5555/3692070.3694094>.